

THE CONTRIBUTION OF AHMAD DONISH TO THE DESCRIPTION OF THE SOCIO-POLITICAL SYSTEM IN THE BUKHARA EMIRATE

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Abstract. In this article, the author analyzes the contribution of Ahmad Donish in describing the socio-political system in the Bukhara Emirate in the historical work of Ahmad Donish "History of the Mangyt Dynasty", the range of problems and current issues. Two works by Ahmad Donish are devoted mainly to problems of history and public administration.

Key words: dynasty, social status, political system, description, analysis, mangyts, historical work.

ВКЛАД АХМАДА ДОНИША В ОПИСАНИЕ ОБЩЕСТВЕННО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье автор анализирует вклад Ахмада Дониша в описании общественно-политического строя в Бухарском эмирате в историческом труде Ахмада Дониша «История династии Мангыт», круг проблем и актуальных вопросов. Две работы Ахмада Дониша посвящены преимущественно проблемам истории и государственного управления.

Ключевые слова: династия, социальный статус, политическая система, описание, анализ, мангыты, исторический труд.

"The sovereign's words should not diverge from deeds. If the sovereign says one thing and does another, then the people can also double-deal. In this case, friends will be split, and enemies united."

Ahmad Donish

Ahmad Donish is a scientist and thinker who created on the threshold of the 19th and 20th centuries. He actively contributed to the development of Eastern historical-philosophical thinking.

He left behind a rich scientific and literary heritage - naturalistic, philosophical and historical works.

The first meetings with the cultural and technical achievements of Europe shook the imagination of Central Asian intellectuals. Trying to understand these previously unknown phenomena, they tried to understand them within the framework of their traditional ideas and Central Asian mentality. As a unique symbol of the primary interaction of two cultural worlds, the idea of a "fire chariot" ("arobai atashi") or "iron chariot" ("arobai ohani"), which represents a new view of the world, can be given as an example. According to Ahmed Donish, this definition means the appearance of railways in Turkestan, and then in Bukhara, and the movement of trains along them. At the same time, in the era when there were no railways, "motor carriage" ("аробай мотор") was used to describe the car in which the local rulers moved around.

For Ahmad Donish, the founder of the enlightenment (modernism) movement in Turkestan, the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, the clash of civilizations is an impetus for the realization of the pains and problems of his country, and the emergence of the idea

of self-realization. . He was one of the first to realize how much the emirate lags behind Russia and European countries. He considered the reason for the backwardness to be the obvious ignorance of the officials and state leaders, as well as the improper implementation of the education and training system. He angrily writes that intelligent thoughts do not reach the ears and that they are engaged in only four things: eating and drinking, littering, collecting and riding a horse ("from khordan, ridan, jamaa kardan and asp davandan" Among the works mentioned above, Donish's "Brief History of the Bukhara Emirs" is undoubtedly the most prominent and significant. (1885-1910) the beginning of the reign, that is, the events that happened before the author's eyes and he was a witness 'focused.

"Brief History of Bukhara Mangit Amirs" became known much later than the time it was written. Now it is difficult to say how familiar this work was to the author's contemporaries, because for a long time there was no mention of this work. It is not shown in any of the tazkiras.

Even though S. Ayni was personally acquainted with Ahmed Donish and considered himself his student, he does not mention this work anywhere. Only in 1936, E. Ye. Bertels reported for the first time that he managed to find the manuscript of A. Donish's hitherto unknown work.

Bertels called it "Treatise" ("Trisol") and gave a brief summary of it in his work.

In 1946, S.U. Ulugzada briefly described the content of this work in his research. The scientific community is familiar with some works of Donish's work, and as a result of scientists' research, a number of manuscripts belonging to Donish's pen were found. In 1959, the first printed edition of Donish's work prepared by R. Hodizoda in new Tajik graphics was published with a number of abbreviations.

The second edition is significantly different from the first in terms of size. In addition, there is a lot of interesting new material in the supplementary text. In particular, there is a preface written by Donish, which allows to describe the author as a historian. The same additional text contains new interesting information about the Chinese-Kipchak uprising in the second half of the 19th century. The author's predictions about irrigation issues, improvement of the country's economic situation and some other details are very interesting.

In 1960, M.N. For the first time, Usmanov translated the work "Brief History of the Mangit Amirs of Bukhara" published under the name "Historical treatise" into Russian. The translation was originally based on the known manuscripts and the first printed edition of the text was published. The translator laid the foundation for the translation of Ahmed Donish's works into Russian.

It should be noted that the title "Risola or a brief history of the Bukhara mangit emirs" is conditional. In the tazkiras and poems of Donish's contemporaries or those who lived after him, only Donish's poetic works and his famous "Navodir ul-wakoe" are mentioned, but as noted above, no information is given about "The Treatise".

E. Ye. Bertels, who made a great contribution to the discovery of this work, calls it "Biography of the Holy Bukhara Emirs" and comments: "I think that this title was added later, after the treatise was written. The author himself simply called it "The Treatise".

"Risola" is a valuable and interesting historical work of the end of the 19th century, but it is unparalleled in its content. Traditionally, it can be divided into two parts that differ in size and importance. In the short first part, the author narrates only the events he heard or received from

written sources. It contains brief information about the last years of the reign of Emir Daniyar and the reign of three emirs - Shahmurad, Haydar and Nasrullah.

It should be noted that Ahmad Donish does not cite the sources from which he got his information. Only two historical works are mentioned in the entire "Treatise": "Tuzuki Timuri" a thirteenth century work of incarnation and "Rawzat al-Safa" works of the nineteenth century.

According to scholars studying the historical works of Akhmed Donish, the currently known historical works on the history of Mangits were written by local authors in the early or middle of the 19th century.

Donish's "Risola" differs from the mentioned works of his contemporaries by the fact that the events in it are given much more widely. In particular, Mirza Azim Somi cares little about the problems of public administration. According to L.M. Yepifanova, the researcher of this historian's work, Mirzo Somiy "never came out with a demand to reform the state structure of the Bukhara Khanate and did not propose any innovations or reconstruction in social and political life."

This is how these two authors evaluate the early years of Amir Muzaffar's reign. Sami: "At the beginning of his reign, Amir Muzaffar made justice his banner and threw a veil of generosity over himself. He treated the Amirs, Sipohis and other inhabitants of the state with various gifts and mercy, and all classes were grateful to him. He performed commendable actions and displayed good behavior."

However, Donish evaluates the current situation of the khanate as follows: "Amir Muzaffar, who strengthened his position on the throne, dealt cruelly with the supporters of the execution of the will. According to the will, the grandson who was supposed to be Nasrullah's heir fled Bukhara and disappeared. Amir killed all his sons and grandsons, not one of them could escape in any area. Soon after, he dismissed the ministers and other high-ranking officials appointed by his father, confiscated their property, and appointed his loyal men in their place.

The army and the people were dissatisfied with these actions of the Amir."

When talking about the Sami emir, following the example of court historians, choosing flattering expressions, he focuses on the details of military operations in the war with the Russians and the neighboring khanates, while Donish gives a broader picture of the situation in the emirate. gives information.

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